

JUSTIFICATION OF THE POTENTIAL CONDENSATE CONTENT IN THE FORMATION GAS

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Abstract

The article discusses the results of complex field studies of gas wells and reservoirs in order to establish the gas dynamic parameters of the reservoir and well and study their gas condensate characteristics at the Altyguyi field. The main attention in the study of the well and the formation was paid to a more accurate determination of the value of the component composition of the formation gas required for the compilation of differential condensation isotherms, determined by sampling raw condensate. Based on the constructed graphs of differential condensation isotherms for gas condensate systems of 3 wells, the pressure of the beginning of condensate separation from natural gas is determined. Based on the results of the conducted research, the justification for the allocation of operational facilities, their drilling systems, taking into account the need for dual completion (DC) in wells, was carried out.

Keywords: stable condensate, molecular weight, isotherm, reservoir gas, differential condensation, condensate loss, perforation.

The substantiation of the potential condensate content in the formation gas was carried out by the method of compiling isotherms of differential condensation of gas condensate systems based on the results of calculations. These isotherms were used to determine the pressure of the beginning of condensation and the potential condensate content in the formation gas [1].

When using this method, the component composition of reservoir gas required for the compilation of differential condensation isotherms, determined by sampling raw condensate into containers during product separation and its further degassing, debutanization in laboratory conditions, for all gas condensate systems is determined by summing $C_{5+above}^{s.g}$ (in separation gas) and $C_{5+above}^{st.c.}$ (content, in % of pentanes and above boiling in stable condensate), calculated from the output of stable condensate q_{st} (cm^3/m^3 , density ρ and molecular weight of stable condensate) by the expression:

$$C_{5+above}^{st.c.} = \frac{2,404 * \rho}{M},$$

where q_{st} is the output of stable condensate, g/m^3 ;

ρ is the density of stable condensate, g/m^3 ;

M is the molecular weight of the condensate.

The value of the molecular weight (M) was not indicated in the studies for condensate systems and was calculated by the formula:

$$M = 44,29 \frac{\rho_{st.c.} + 0,004}{1,034 - \rho_{st.c.}},$$

The remaining components are accepted unchanged.

Next, we calculate the composition of the reservoir gas:

$$1) C_4^{g.s} - C_{5+above}^{st.c.} = CH_4^{res.g.}$$

$$2) C_{5+above}^{g.s} - C_{5+above}^{st.c.} = CH_{5+above}^{res.g.}$$

The indicators of the constructed graph of differential condensation isotherms are given in Tables 1 and 2, and their results in Tables 3 and 4.

Based on the constructed graphs of differential condensation isotherms for gas condensate systems of 3 wells, the pressure of the beginning of condensate separation from natural gas is determined, the values of which are equal to or close to the initial reservoir pressure of the well (see tables 3, 4 and Fig. 1-3).

Table 1
Information for calculating the differential condensation isotherms for the gas condensate system by the PS/AT PC program

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	N ₂	CO ₂	H ₂ S	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	C ₄ H ₁₀	
									nor	izo
2(III)	NK-7d	3512-3522	0,87	0,25	-	96,7	0,71	0,29	0,1	0,08
1(II)	NK -8	3616-3625	0,32	0,2	-	96,7	0,91	0,26	0,1	0,08
5(I)	NK -7d	3618-3624	-	0,2	-	97,0	0,96	0,24	0,07	0,07

Table 2

Information for calculating the differential condensation isotherms for the gas condensate system by the PS/AT PC program

№ well	$C_{5+above}^{s,g}$	Stable condensate output	T_{res}	M	Fractional composition of the condensate mixture %					
					begining of boiling $^{\circ}C$	10	50	90	end of boiling $^{\circ}C$	rema- ins
2(III)	0,87	0,25	-	96,72	0,71	0,29	0,1	0,08		
1(II)	0,32	0,2	-	96,75	0,91	0,26	0,1	0,08		
5(I)	-	0,2	-	97,02	0,96	0,24	0,07	0,07		

Table 3

The results of the calculation of the differential condensation isotherms for the gas condensate system by the PS/AT PC program

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Pressure kgf/s^2		
			Formation (initial)	The beginning of condensation	Expedient condensation
2(III)	<i>NK 7d</i>	3512-3522	510	518	50-80
1(II)	<i>NK -8</i>	3616-3625	496	494	50-80
5(I)	<i>NK -7d</i>	3618-3624	524	526	50-80

Table 4

The results of the calculation of the differential condensation isotherms for the gas condensate system by the PS/AT PC program

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Stable condensate output (initial), cm^3/m^3	Amount of potential condensate g/m^3	Density of stable condensate g/cm^3
2(III)	<i>NK -7d</i>	3512-3522	86,2	69,5	0,7877
1(II)	<i>NK -8</i>	3616-3625	118,4	93,2	0,7959
5(I)	<i>NK -7d</i>	3618-3624	103	96,5	0,7910

Figure 1. Graph of isotherms of differential condensation of the gas condensate system of well № 2 (III) on the Altyguyi field

Figure 2. Graph of isotherms of differential condensation of the gas condensate system of well № 1 (II) on the Altuguyi field

Figure 3. Graph of isotherms of differential condensation of the gas condensate system of well № 5 (I) on the Altuguyi field

From the constructed isotherms, the amount of condensate content in 1 m³ of reservoir gas for wells № 2 (III), №.1 (II) and 5 (I) respectively obtained 69.5 g/m³, 95.2g/m³ and 96.5g/m³. Potential stability of condensate, g/cm³

Therefore, in the composition of 1m³ reservoir gas, the amount of condensate content is assumed for

the horizon for the horizon NK_{7d} 80.5 g/m³ and the horizon NK₈ 95.2g/m³ [2].

Based on the results of the developed differential condensation isotherms, the beginning of the condensation pressure for the III well object №. 2 is 518 kg/cm² (P_{res}=510 kg/cm²), for the II well object №.1 496 kg/cm² (P_{res}=494 kg/cm²) and for the I well object №. 5 526 kg/cm² (P_{res} =524 kg/cm²).

During the periods of gas-hydrodynamic studies and pilot operation of gas condensate deposits of the field, due to the absence of experimental installations UGK-3, UFR, thermodynamic studies to determine the recovery coefficient and condensate losses for gas condensate deposits of the Altyguyi field were not carried out. These parameters were determined from the equation:

$$\sigma = 11,325 + 0,105 P_{res}^{init}$$

P_{res}^{init} - initial reservoir pressure, kgf/cm²;
 σ - condensate losses in the reservoir, %.

The above expression is derived from the graph (see Fig. 4-5), plotted in coordinates $\delta = f(P_{res}^{init})$.

Figure 4. Dependence of the initial reservoir pressure on the volume of condensate loss in the formations of the Gogerendag-Ekerem fields

Figure 5. Dependence of the initial reservoir pressure on the volume of condensate loss in the reservoirs of the fields of South-Western Turkmenistan

It should be emphasized that this dependence was revealed on the basis of numerous experimental studies on the installations of RUT, UGK-3 systems of gas condensate deposits of Southwestern Turkmenistan, which have common specific features, as well as an undoubted genetic community.

This method has been sufficiently tested and is widely used in determining losses and the coefficient of condensate extraction from the subsurface [3].

Certain values of the pressure of the beginning of condensation; the potential condensate content in the reservoir gas; reservoir losses and the condensate recovery coefficient obtained from the dependence:

$$\sigma = f(P_{res}^{init}) \text{ for all investigated objects.}$$

$\sigma = f(P_{res}^{init})$ the dependence of the specified volume of condensate loss in the reservoir and the coefficient of condensate recovery for the horizons NK_{7d} and

NK_8 due to the proximity of the depth of occurrence (location) and the initial pressure, the value for the two horizons is assumed to be the same, respectively 65.6% and 0.344.

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МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИХ МЕТОДИК ПОУЗЛОВОГО АНАЛИЗА ОЧАГОВ ПОТЕРЬ ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИИ В РАСПРЕДЕЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ СЕТЯХ 10/6/0,4 кВ

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MODERNIZATION OF EXISTING TECHNIQUES FOR PER-COST ANALYSIS OF POWER LOSS POINTS IN 10/6/0.4 kV DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

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Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены основные направления совершенствования некоторых методик определения коммерческих потерь электрической энергии, учета отпущенной в распределительную сеть и полезно потребленной электроэнергии, которые позволят вычислить потери электроэнергии в электросети, разработать программу по снижению потерь и уменьшить финансовых убытков сетевой организации.

Важность решения задач заключается в том, что организация, осуществляющая услуги по передаче электроэнергии обязана компенсировать фактические потери электрической энергии в своих сетях с помощью их покупки на оптовом рынке электроэнергии.

При расчете тарифа на оплату услуг по передаче электроэнергии по распределительным сетям электроснабжающих компаний предусматривается величина нормативных технологических потерь электроэнергии. Во многих сетевых организациях фактические потери электрической энергии больше нормативных технологических потерь. Следовательно, сетевая организация, которая оплачивает фактические потери электроэнергии и получает компенсацию в объеме стоимости нормативных технологических потерь электроэнергии, переносит финансовые убытки.

Abstract

The article discusses the main directions for improving some methods for determining the commercial losses of electrical energy, accounting for the electricity supplied to the distribution network and usefully consumed electricity, which will allow calculating the losses of electricity in the power grid, developing a program to reduce losses and reduce the financial losses of the grid organization.

The importance of solving problems lies in the fact that an organization providing electricity transmission services is obliged to compensate for the actual losses of electrical energy in its networks by purchasing them on the wholesale electricity market.

When calculating the tariff for payment for services for the transmission of electricity through the distribution networks of power supply companies, the value of standard technological losses of electricity is provided. In many network organizations, the actual losses of electrical energy are greater than the normative technological losses. Consequently, the grid organization, which pays for the actual losses of electricity and receives compensation in the amount of the cost of standard technological losses of electricity, suffers financial losses.

Ключевые слова: нормирование потерь электроэнергии, сравнительный анализ, постоянные потери энергии, нагрузочные потери энергии.